

The Trypophobia Questionnaire English version

Trypophobic images

1. Have goosebumps
 2. Feel like going crazy
 3. Body trembles
 4. Overwhelmed by fear
 5. Become anxious, feel terror and dread
 6. Feel aversion or repulsion
 7. Get goosebumps
 8. Feel unwell, feel like vomiting
 9. Feel chills
 10. Feel like panicking, want to scream
 11. Feel nervous (e.g., rapid heartbeat, sweating, stomach ache, etc.)
 12. Have difficulty breathing
 13. Feel uncomfortable or restless
 14. Feel itchy
 15. Feel like crying
 16. Vomit
 17. Have a sudden urge to destroy the holes
- Option: Do not feel at all (1)/ Barely feel (2)/ Slightly feel (3)/ Considerably feel (4)/
Feel extremely strong (5)